

NEOLOGISMS IN DIGITAL MASS MEDIA

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Ina Voloşciuc

Moldova State University

ORCID 0000-0001-7642-8255

The article under consideration is to investigate the creation and spread of newly coined words, phrases or familiar words used in a new sense in the “Fourth Estate” or the digital media and analyse their word formation process. The digital media contributes to creating favourable conditions for the boost of neologisms which react to the changes that take place in every society and explain the emergence of new lexemes or give a modern touch to known words within the digital ecosystem.

Keywords : *neologisms, mass media, digital media, word formation, combining.*

Introduction

Modern mass media contributes to creating favourable conditions for the boost of neologisms, newly coined words, phrases or familiar words used in a new sense (Collins COBUILD Dictionary), which react to the changes that take place in every modern society, explain the emergence of new lexemes or give a modern touch to known words within the digital ecosystem. One reason we deploy neologisms is that existing words are bleached by overuse (Hitchings, 2011), once viewed with scepticism, today accepted, as nobody can be surprised with such words as *artificial intelligence, sudoku, hackathon, crowdfunding* or *cyber ambassador*, that have already become part of our lives. According to Global Language Monitor “...around 5,400 new words are created every year; it’s only the 1,000 or so deemed to be in sufficiently widespread use that make it into print” (Bodle, 2016).

The digitalization of the “Fourth Estate that serves as a platform for diverse voices and perspectives” (Political Dictionary Online), has allowed the mass media companies reach the audience easier to disseminate information, deliver news faster to the target groups, granting people access to a variety of media platforms, receive the feedback from readers in comments, thus growing interactivity between both parties. The phrase the “Fourth Estate” was created to point out the power of press, its influence on the public opinion. The situation has not changed, as well as the media endorsement, importance and influence of the watchdog on the political, economic, cultural and social spheres. Therefore, the article under consideration is to identify and investigate the morphology of such neologisms in the “Fourth Estate” or digital media, such as BBC, The Guardian, Glamour Magazine, People Management, Gulf News, The New York Times, Harper’s BAZAAR, Daily Mail, Real Researcher, The Washington Post, New York Post, Forbes, Politico, as well as other digital sources and analyse their word formation process. The main criteria of selection of neologisms were newness and novelty of the linguistic units, used to reflect the realities of the last three years (2021-2023), their assimilation by the speakers and identification of productive word-formation processes.

Methodology and analysis

The present study has used the descriptive-qualitative method of analyzing the morphological structures of the neologisms used in digital media, then investigated the

morphological processes to classify one hundred neologisms (Cambridge Dictionary Blog), identified in electronic mass media, using the model of John Algeo and defined by the digital Cambridge Dictionary. Therefore, John Algeo distinguishes seven etymological sources for new words (Algeo, 1991): *creating* (a new word that is made from nothing or “scratch, creation ex nihilo”), *borrowing* (a new word borrowed from another language), *combining* (a new word created through a combination of existing words and word parts), *shortening* (a new word can be created by omitting some part of an old word), *blending* (the process of simultaneously combining and shortening), *shifting* (derivation of a new lexeme from an existing one without a specific morphological marker indicating the change of word class and meaning) and *unknown source* (origins are unknown in whole or in part).

One hundred neo lexemes, selected from the digital media was categorized in accordance with their ways of word formation, see Table 1. Therefore, the present article has identified three main pro-active categories and they are combining, blending and shortening that coincided to the research carried out in 2019. The most dynamic process remains combining that is used to create neologisms in 81% of the total amount of 100 neologisms.

Table 1. Pro-active main categories of word formation.

The words presented below have been selected from A Blog About Words from Cambridge Dictionary that monitors the emergence of neologisms in mass media. Taking into account different possibilities provided by combining we can distinguish firstly compounds that resulted from the combination of existing words and word parts that proves to be the most productive method. This type is rich in words from different spheres of human activity. To begin with the neologisms that have been developed to show the importance of digital technologies. Therefore, we should mention such words as artificial intelligence (the use or study of computer systems or machines that have some of the qualities that the human brain has, such as the ability to interpret and produce language in a way that seems human, recognize or create images, solve problems, and learn from data supplied to them), chatbot (a computer program designed to have a conversation with a human being), machine learning (a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) and computer science which focuses on the use of data and algorithms to imitate the way that humans learn, gradually improving its accuracy), conversational commerce (the use of chatbots

and other machine learning technology to make people feel they are talking to a real person when they buy things, ask for advice etc. online), ghost work (work done by a human being, usually online and for low pay, to do a task that most people believe is done automatically by a computer), voice cloning (the use of artificial intelligence to make recordings that sound like the voice of a specific person). Certain words help us track the impact of social media, as people use it not only to relax and chat with friends, but also to work. Therefore, the following words have been identified: *screen apnea* (the situation where someone stops breathing properly when they are looking at the screen of their mobile phone or similar device), *soft troll* (a person who criticizes or makes nasty comments about someone on the internet but only to other people and not directly to the person in question), *rage farming* (the activity of posting content on social media that aims to make the reader angry and then share the content with other users), *sky computing* (a way of accessing services, apps etc. on different systems on the internet through a top level to which all the systems belong), *crypto winter* (a situation when the price of cryptocurrency falls and remains very low for a long period of time), *bossware* (a type of software that employers can use to monitor what their employees are doing on their computers), *cyber ambassador* (a person who helps other people use the internet safely and protect themselves and their computer information against crime or attacks carried out online), *millennial pause* (a very short pause before someone starts speaking on a video they are recording for social media to make sure the camera is recording, said to be a common practice among millennials (people born between around 1981 and 1996)), *green noise* (a mixture of sounds or electrical signals that resembles sounds heard in nature, such as waterfalls or rustling leaves, and is thought to help people to relax), *digital removalist* (someone whose job is to remove any content from a person's social media posts that may harm their reputation), *productivity theatre* (a way someone behaves at work that makes them appear to be working very hard, even if this is not the case), *boomerang employee* (someone who goes back to work for a company they have already worked for in the past), *micromobility* (the use of small electric vehicles such as e-scooters, normally used for travelling short distances within towns and cities), *crypto mugging* (the illegal activity of attacking someone in order to steal their mobile phone and use it to take control of their cryptocurrency), *dark post* (a message or advertisement on a website or social media platform that cannot be seen by everyone, only by the people who are the intended target), *quantum apocalypse* (the situation where extremely powerful computers can access all encrypted data very quickly and easily, making all hidden information public), *vampire device* (an electrical appliance that continues to use electricity when it is switched on but not being used), *clean inboxer* (someone who reads and takes action on every email they receive when they receive it, so that there are never any unread emails in their inbox), *tattleware* (software that allows an employer to monitor the activity of someone who is working from home, in particular to make sure the employee is working when they are supposed to be), *blogroll* (a list of links to blogs), *blogosphere* (all the blogs (records of personal thoughts and opinions) on the internet, and the people who write or read them). There are words that combine social media with family matters, such as *password child* (a humorous way of referring to a parent's favorite child, supposedly because the parent will often use the name of that child as a computer password), *Generation Beta* (a humorous way of referring to a parent's favourite child, supposedly because the parent will often use the name of that child as a computer password).

Another important field is labour that has also expanded the amount of active words, by implementing *September Surge* (an increase in job vacancies that is said to happen in September every year), *loud labourer* (someone who likes to tell colleagues about how busy and successful

they are at work, when often this is not actually the case), *power skills* (a set of abilities that are essential for doing your job well but are not specific to any one job), *shift shock* (a feeling of surprise and disappointment when you start a new job and discover that it, or the company, is not as good as you expected), *lazy girl job* (a job that is well paid, does not demand long hours or too much effort, and can often be done remotely), *climate quitting* (the act of leaving your job because the organization where you work is not doing enough to fight climate change), *proximity bias* (the way in which people, usually managers, are more likely to treat an employee better if the employee is physically present in the workplace rather than working remotely), *friendshoring* (the practice of operating a business or part of a business in a country that is an ally), *mind gym* (a place or club where you can go to do classes and have treatments that improve your mental health), *rage applying* (the activity of impulsively applying for several new jobs only because your present job is currently making you unhappy or angry), *quiet thriving* (the activity of making small changes to the way you work to help you feel happier and more fulfilled in your job), *hustle culture* (the idea that work must be the the most important thing in your life and that working long hours and not taking time off is the only way to achieve success), *Bare Minimum Mondays* (the trend of doing as little as possible at work on Mondays in order to reduce stress during the rest of the week), *the Great Regret* (a trend in the employment market that has seen many people who left their jobs during the Great Resignation regret their decision), *quiet quitting* (the activity of doing the minimum amount of work needed to keep one's job but with no enthusiasm or commitment), *ghost colleague* (an employee of a company who works alone, often at home, and is not in frequent contact with other people who work for the same company), *jobfishing* (the illegal practice of recruiting people to work for a company that does not exist in order to trick them into sending their personal information and working without being paid).

As to finance A Blog About Words from Cambridge Dictionary has suggested the following neologisms: *bucket budgeting* (a way of organizing your finances that involves saving money in a different bank account for each type of bill or purchase), *bougie broke* (a way of organizing your finances that involves saving money in a different bank account for each type of bill or purchase), *financial cleanse* (a detailed examination of your finances to identify ways of saving money and spending less), *Great Wealth Transfer* (the gradual movement of money from baby boomers (people born in the mid-1940s to mid-1960s) to younger generations, either given as gifts or passed on through inheritance), *blandstanding* (wearing clothes that are simple and practical, although very expensive), *quiet luxury* (a fashion trend where clothing is of very high quality, well-cut and in neutral colors).

Socialization has developed the words like *wokefishing* (pretending to care more than you actually do about social problems such as racism and inequality in order to attract someone you want to have a romantic relationship with), *social omnivore* (a person who never eats meat at home but sometimes eats it when in a restaurant or at someone else's house), *friendship recession* (a period when many people have few or no friends), *thrift flipping* (the activity of buying second-hand clothes, turning them into new, more attractive items and sometimes selling them for a higher price), *mind dieting* (the activity of thinking carefully about what you eat in a way that motivates you to choose foods that are better for you), *nepo baby* (the child of an actor, a musician etc. who achieves success because of their famous parent), *time millionaire* (someone who places more importance on the amount of free time they have than on how much money they earn).

Here we can also see new formations that remind us of the recent Covid-19 pandemic, as we can still see its impact on people's health: *pandemic brain* (a series of symptoms including forgetting things and not being able to think clearly that people are said to experience as a result

of the Covid-19 pandemic, even if they have not had Covid) is being actively used, *digital amnesia* (a condition where people become less able to remember things because they are used to looking everything up on the internet), *flu hunter* (a scientist who looks for new strains of flu so that an effective vaccine can be developed).

To wrap up the first sub-category of compounds that resulted from the combination of existing words and word parts, it is worth mentioning *cosy crime* (a type of crime fiction that is light-hearted and often humorous, is set in a small community and does not feature explicit violence), as well as *porch piracy* (the act of stealing a package that has been delivered and left outside someone's house) to inform about their existence.

Secondly, the usage of prefixes. Traditional prefixes widely used to create new words are anti-, bi-, contro-, crypto-, de-, hydro-, hyper-, inter-, mega-, multi-, neo-, non-, post-, re-, ultra-, un-, under-, urbi-, etc: *de-influencing* (the activity of describing certain products on social media and saying why you would not), *anti-haul* (a type of social media content where someone describes a number of products that they do not think their followers should buy), *anti-perk* (an advantage someone is given because of their job that is in fact not useful or helpful), *micromobility* (a way of guiding endangered species of moth to an area where they will be able to survive), *superalignment* (the study of how to control superintelligent AIs that may be built in the future so that they act in ways that are useful and not harmful to human beings), *superdodger* (someone who is resistant to a particular virus), *supercloud* (a single computing system where services such as storage, apps etc. from different providers can be easily accessed by the user), *exascale* (An exascale computer is very powerful, able to carry out one quintillion (10¹⁸) mathematical operations per second), *recommerce* (the practice of buying and selling used goods online, usually on websites created for this purpose).

Thirdly, the usage of traditional suffixes, or combination of suffixes: -able, -ate, -ation, -ed, -ee, -er, -fication, -ian, -y, -ism, -ity, -ization, -ize, -less, -phobe, etc., as in neologisms *burn-on* (a feeling of stress and exhaustion experienced by someone who has been working too hard for a long period but continues to be good at their job and appears to be enjoying it), *blogging* (the activity of writing blogs), *blogger* (someone who writes a blog), *rust-out* (a feeling of extreme boredom and lack of enthusiasm, caused by not having enough to do at work or working on unfulfilling tasks for too long), *resenteeism* (a new workplace term that describes the feeling of staying in a job despite being fundamentally unhappy), *jugging* (a theft committed by a perpetrator who waits at a bank, near an ATM, or outside an expensive store, watches for customers who might be carrying a large amount of cash or goods, and then follows them to steal the money or goods from the customer or from their car), *computing* (the leading information resource for technology decision makers, providing the latest market news and hard-hitting opinion).

The next most productive process is blending with 14% of the following neologisms: *AIgicism* (the process or practice of using AI (= artificial intelligence) tools to write essays or answer exam questions and pretending that it is your own work), *mpox* (a new word for monkeypox (= a disease caused by a virus that can be spread to humans by monkeys, apes, rats, and other animals), *fexting* (the act of fighting with someone by exchanging text messages rather than speaking on the phone or in person), *rom-con* (a situation where a criminal tricks someone into a fake romantic relationship and exploits their trust to get money or personal information out of them), *infostealer* (a type of computer software that has been deliberately designed to steal information such as passwords, bank account details etc.), *frolleague* (a colleague who becomes a friend), *virovore* (an organism that eats viruses), *gamevertising* (a way of advertising a product

by making it appear in a computer game), *tripledeemic* (the widespread outbreak of Covid-19, flu and respiratory syncytial virus at the same time), *romantasy* (a type of book that is part romance and part fantasy), *algspeak* (words used on social media posts as a way of avoiding using other words that algorithms will identify as unsuitable or inappropriate), *Novid* (someone who has never had the Covid-19 virus), *splinternet* (the idea that there is, or could be, different versions of the internet rather than one global version, usually because the governments of some countries have blocked or restricted parts of its content) (Cambridge Dictionary Blog).

Then goes shortening, that takes 5 % out of 100 neologisms, with lexemes, *AGI* (artificial general intelligence), *RLHF* (reinforcement learning from human feedback), *RTO* (return to office), *WFC* (working from cafés), *DAO* (an organization or company that exists online) were identified.

As to the other categories as creating, it is rather complicated to make something from nothing, that is why it remains the least productive of the six. Shifting has also 1%, it can be grammar and meaning, however, the circumstances of the use, as well as the form should be analyzed more carefully. The unknown source that has 0% speaks about uncertainty of the origin in this category and is rarely used.

Conclusion

Combining provides the most creative way of emergence of neologisms and is far more dynamic, as well as widely used in the English language, due to simplicity of combining existing words, changing their initial meaning by derivation and play of prefixes and suffixes, that gives such words a new chance of manifesting themselves. The role of creativity, inspired by social changes, remains an efficient means of grasping attention of the reader when reading the digital press, as existing words are bleached by overuse. Trying to live their lives as quickly as possible, modern people are using available instruments to express themselves quickly, clearly and promptly, therefore, utilizing known words and transforming them into something new and unique, transforming them into neologisms and spreading them thanks to digital media that contributes to creating favourable conditions for their boost.

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